

Industrial Profile of Jammu & Kashmir State

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ABSTRACT

Infrastructure development serves as an engine for industrial development and calls for continuous attention of the Government. Development of Industrial Estates /Infrastructure is the major function of the Industries and Commerce Department. The State has 53 existing industrial estates spread over an area of 3135 Kanals of land use position ending November, 2013. There are 53 Industrial Estates in the State spread over an area of 31,335 Kanals. 29 new Industrial Estates are at different stages of development. There is huge scope in the state for taking up of manufacturing activities in the field of Food processing, Meat processing (Mutton/Chicken), Leather, Pharmaceuticals, wood based Industries Viz sports goods/bats/willow wicker etc, high grade raw silk, woollen fabrics, computer/electronics and Information Technology. Jammu and Kashmir offers good market for all types of consumer goods in view of its population being more than 1.25 crore and a vast floating population in the shape of tourists (over 1 million per year) and yatries (over 15 million per year) visiting the State for leisure and pilgrimage respectively.

Keywords: *Infrastructure, Commerce, Food processing, Woollen fabrics etc.*

INTRODUCTION

The economy of the Jammu and Kashmir state is predominantly agricultural. The state offers a challenge to both the planners and administrators in dealing the various problems coupled with the economic backwardness of the state. Inclusivity and equity of the growth and development process alongside with its sustainability has to be the most important idea of the developmental efforts. While imperatives of soaring growth and development are well understood, distributive characteristic of the

growth is also important. In the background of the obtaining state of affairs in the state, the test of ensuring participatory and fair regional development becomes exceptionally essential. (Economic survey 2014-15)

The economic criss-cross of the state studies in different regions. For instance Kashmir valley is also known for its sericulture and cold-water fisheries. Apart from this Wood from Kashmir region is used to make high-quality furniture especially cricket bats, popularly known as Kashmir Willow. Kashmiri saffron is also very famous and brings the state a handsome amount of foreign exchange. Agricultural exports from Jammu and Kashmir include apples, barley, cherries, corn, millet, oranges, rice, peaches, pears, saffron, vegetables, and wheat, while manufactured exports include handicrafts, rugs, and shawls.

Horticulture plays a vital role in the economic development of the state, almost 33 lakh population is engage with it directly or indirectly, 24.94 LMTs with turnover of s. 6000.00 crore roughly for the period of 2015-16, this sector is the next biggest source of income in the state's economy. The Kashmir region is known for its horticulture industry and is the wealthiest region in the state Horticultural produce from the state includes apples, apricots, cherries, pears, plums, almonds and walnuts.

One of the major handicaps faced by small-scale industries in India has been either lack, or insufficient infrastructure facilities. In order to provide small-scale units the proximity of other industrial units, the idea of establishing industrial estates was first adopted in India by the Small-Scale Industries Board (SSIB) at its meeting held in January 1955.

As a result, the first industrial estate in India was set up at Rajkot in Gujarat in September 1955. Since then, there is no looking back. By now, the number of industrial estates in the country had gone up to more than 650 making it the largest programme of its kind in the world.

The objectives tagged to the programme included to give boost to the growth of small-scale industries in the country, to disperse industry outside metropolitan towns, to relocate existing units operating in congested areas, to provide subcontracting opportunities to small industry and to improve operational efficiency of small units through common facilities. However, research studies report findings contrary to it. The units working outside industrial estates have performed better than units working inside the industrial estates.

METHODOLOGY

Methodology' is a technique in which we do work in a systematic way. Methodology play a vital role in the representation and expression of factual knowledge in a systematic and synthesized manner whenever a branch of any discipline based on or concerned with the facts of knowledge is rejected or selected; it is always based on methodology. Discipline is synthesis not by its subject matter but by its methodology is a key to re presentation, expression and analysis of the field work. In simple words, methodology refers to the research technique to the discipline. The presenting study is empirical in nature where information has been collected by district industrial centre kathua, statistics of industries from industrial website of Jammu and Kashmir and by using various website on the internet.

The data for the completion of my present dissertation have been taken from the primary as well as secondary source. The major source of data is listed below:

1. The primary data including first hand reports both published and unpublished from various govt and private institutions. Various website on internet, newspapers.
2. Secondary sources include journals, research articles and books.

Results and Discussion

J & K has not been able to attract investments in this sector and remained an industrially backward state due to its unique economic disadvantages arising out

of remoteness and poor connectivity, hilly and often inhospitable terrain, weak resource base, poor infrastructure, sparse population density, shallow markets and most importantly the political uncertainty. Moreover the natural factors are more conducive for handicrafts, village and Small Scale Industries and less to large and heavy industries. Nevertheless, despite all odds and limitations the Jammu & Kashmir State is on the path of industrialization in a modest way. Many small and medium-scale industries have come up basically in the traditional sectors along with some new areas like food processing, agro-based units and metallic and non metallic products. Besides, due to saturation of employment opportunities in the government/traditional non-governmental sectors like Agriculture, Industrial sector has been declared as the main vehicle for accelerating economic tempo besides providing employment to the educated unemployed youth in the State.

Industrial development always remains a thrust area in the Government agenda. Government's endeavour is to provide efficient and cost effective infrastructure, skilled human resources, stable environment and good governance which are the pre-requisites for creating a proper investment environment for sustainable industrial growth. Dispersal of industries to the 266 underdeveloped areas in the state through creation of necessary infrastructure and providing financial /fiscal incentives is focused. In the perspective of industrial growth, Industries and Commerce Department has been established with a well knit system for carrying its activities effectively. The Industries and Commerce Department is concentrating to attract investment in the State for developing world class infrastructure to achieve objectives like:

1. To explore available resources in the State.
2. To create conducive industrial employment.
3. To promote labour intensive industries to lessen the pressure on unemployment market in the State.

The Industrial sector is now an important source because of its dual role in the economic growth and development of the State as well as in generating employment opportunities and source of livelihood for the unemployed youth. Industrial sector contributes 25.87% to GSDP (gross domestic Product) of State at stable 2004-05 prices. The State has 53 existing industrial estates which stretch over the huge area of 32034 Kanals of land as per position ending November 2014.

DIRECTORATE OF INDUSTRIES AND COMMERCE, KASHMIR

The Directorate of Industries & Commerce, Kashmir is the foremost association which deals with all aspects of arrangement and progress of small scale and minute industrial units in the Division. It acts through 12 District Centres (DICs), one in each district as mentioned in Table I. Apart from creating infrastructural amenities for industrial improvement in the profile of establishing industrial estates, export promotion parks and growth centres where fully-developed land, power, water roads et al, are existing and where potential entrepreneurs are encouraged to establish their ventures, the Directorate provides amenities of according to a variety of registrations, imparting instruction to entrepreneurs, coordinating with a choice of sister agencies, by giving way to different State/Central Government incentives to various industrial units.

DIRECTORATE OF INDUSTRIES AND COMMERCE JAMMU

The Directorate of Industries & Commerce was bifurcated in year 2007 into two Directorates i.e. one for Jammu Division and other for Kashmir Division. A devoted Government and progressively more reactive organisation is rolling hard work to be consisted and constant in promoting investments with on attractive package of incentives the state is emerging as a land of opportunities for investments, those who are already here are happy & many are proposing to expand. The existing industrial estates in the state managed by Directorate of Industries and commerce is with no. of units .About 10,000 Kanals of land is 34 being acquired under 18 Land Acquisition cases to develop new Industrial Estates or to expand the existing Industrial Estates across the state as mentioned in Table II.

JAMMU AND KASHMIR STATE INDUSTRIAL DEVELOPMENT CORPORATION LIMITED (SIDCO)

State Industrial Development Corporation Limited was established under the Companies Act of 1956 in the year 1969 as a premier Organization of the State Govt and is primarily responsible for the promotion and development of Medium and Large Scale industries in the State. Functions/duties assigned to SIDCO

➤ Development of Medium & Large Scale Industries

- Creation of Industrial Infrastructure in terms of Industrial Estates.
- Assistance to States for Development of Export Infrastructure & Allied Activities (ASIDE) Scheme of Ministry of Commerce & Industry (Govt. of India).
- Ministry of Food Processing Industries, Govt. of India.
- Mission Directorate for National Mission for Food Processing Industries, Ministry of Food Processing, Govt. of India.
- Disbursement of Soft Loan.
- Executing Agency for Infrastructural Projects for Govt. Corporations wherein work contracts are allotted to SIDCO.
- Executing Agency for Development of Infrastructure of Trade Facilitation Centre, Salembad, and Uri.

JAMMU AND KASHMIR SMALL SCALE INDUSTRIES DEVELOPMENT CORPORATION LIMITED (SICOP)

J & K Small Scale Industries Development Corporation Limited (SICOP) has been established in November 1975 as a fully owned Government Undertaking to aid, assist and promote small-scale industrial sector in J & K State. The Corporation has expanded its areas of operation and today it has District Offices in all 22 District headquarters as given in Table II. At present SICOP is managing and administering nine Industrial Estates namely I/E Gangyal, Birpur, Kathua, ID Centre, Kathua & IID Centre, Udhampur in Jammu and I/E Zainakote, I/E Zakura, Silk/Handicraft Park, Zakura and Sports Goods Complex, Bijbehara in Kashmir Division. Sports Goods Complex, Bijbehara was under the occupation of Security Forces since 1990 and has now been vacated by the Security Forces in October, 2013. These estates are spread over an area of 4617 Kanals and 1208 number of units have been allotted land till date. Functions of SICOP The main objectives of the Corporation as per the Articles 35 and Memorandum of Association of the Corporation are:

- To develop infrastructural facilities in the form of industrial estates;
- To reimburse VAT to the local industrial units who purchase their raw material through SICOP;
- To procure and sell industrial raw materials to the SSI units;
- To extend marketing support to the SSI units;
- To provide Testing Facilities to the industry.

From the above Table III it can be understood that the whole industrial infrastructure is managed by the three important managing agencies that is directorate of industries and commerce, the total number of industrial estates managed by the agency is 33 and based on all three regions of the state. The second most important agency is Jammu and Kashmir state industrial development corporation and the industrial estates are managed by them are 11 in numbers. The third main agency is Jammu and Kashmir small scale industrial development corporation total numbers of industrial estates established by this agency are 9, and all these 3 main agencies play an important role for the growth and development of industrial estates in all three regions of the state. For this reason it can be concluded that the overall industrial estates managed by these three agencies are 53 in figures and the area covered by these estates are 31335 Kanals and it presents 4691 units.

There are 13 districts in all three regions of Jammu and Kashmir where industrial estates have been set up off. In Kashmir region there are 6 districts where 25 numbers of industrial estates has been established that covers 12,105 Kanals of land they share 55% of land towards industrial estates. In Jammu region 5 districts has 13 industrial estates that covers 8,824.23 kanals of land and there share is 41.72%. The Ladakh region due to hilly terrain there is less development of industrial estates however there are 2 number of industrial estates in Leh and Kargil district that covers only 616 Kanals of land area and contributes 2.88 % of land towards the industrial development.

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Table I: Industrial Estates Managed by the Directorate of Industries Kashmir

S. No.	Name of the Estate	Area (In Kanals)	Total no. of units
1	BAMK Srinagar	144	110
2	Ganderbal	106	33
3	Barzulla	102	67
4	Pulwama	24	04
5	Chattapora	96	19
6	Shopian	62	10
7	Anantnagh	57	49
8	Anchidora	86	48
9	Bijbehara	27	25
10	Kulgam	19	10
11	Baramulla	58	26
12	Sopore	82	23
13	Sumbal	45	06
14	Bandipora	01	02
15	Branwari	15	07
16	Leh	237	52
17	Kargil	09	10
18	Khurbathang	31	16

Table II: Industrial Estates Managed by the Directorate of Industries in Jammu.

S. No.	Name of the Estate	Area (In Kanals)	Total no. of units
1	Digiana	137.09	106
2	Jammu Cantt	96.00	34
3	Akhnoor	29.05	21
4	Samba	20.00	13
5	Udhampur	49.04	22
6	Reasi (Gran)	25.00	0
7	Kathua	376.08	85
8	Hiranagar	52.06	24
9	Billawar	53.00	7
10	Kheora, Rajouri	52.00	51
11	Poonch	29.07	44
12	Sangrambata, Kishtwar	42.15	8
13	Dandi Bhaderwah, Doda	54.06	0

Table III: Industrial infrastructure

Managing agency	Industrial Estates(No.)	Area (Kanals)	Units set up (No.)
J & K DIC	32	2517	1175
J & K SIDCO	12	24201	2307
J & K SICOP	9	4617	1209
Total	53	31335	4691

Table IV: Industrial Estates Managed by DIC, SIDCO and SICOP in all three regions of Jammu and Kashmir.

Regions	DIC		SICOP		SIDCO	
	No. of estates	Land	No. Of estates	Land	No. Of estates	Land
Kashmir	18	1305	4	2311	5	8635
Jammu	13	1016	4	3341	4	13028
Ladakh	2	270	1	89.55	2	2038
Total	33	2591	9	5742	11	23701